

Performance of cold-tolerant varieties in western hills of Nepal

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A large portion of rice in Nepal is grown at 1000-2000 m above sea level, where low temperatures cause cold damage. Most varieties grown in high altitudes are indigenous. We evaluated 28 genotypes in 1989 at our Chhomro off-station research site (2000 m above sea level). They were indigenous varieties Raksali, Palung 2, and Chhomro local and materials obtained from IRRI, and the Nepal Rice Improvement Program, Parwanipur, and Botany Division, Khumaltar.

Water temperature during anthesis (Oct-Nov) was 20.2 °C; mean minimum temperatures were 15.1-16.5 °C; mean maximum, 16.3-19.7 °C. During early seedling growth (Jun-Jul), minimum temperatures were 14.5-16.4 °C and maximum temperatures, 21.9-23.1 °C.

Agronomic traits for cold tolerance were good in some exotic varieties (see table). Spikelet sterility was 100% in all genotypes except Chhomro local (14%) and Seto Bhakunde (25%). Those local varieties produced some yield.

Internationally known cold-tolerant

Some agronomic traits^a of selected cold-tolerant rice genotypes at Chhomro (altitude 2000 m), Nepal, 1989.

Genotype	Plant vigor (1-9 scale)	Tillering ability (1-9 scale)	Cold tolerance (1-9 scale)	Panicle exertion (1-9 scale)	Sheath rot (1-9 scale)
Akiyudaka	7	9	5	5	3
Chhomro Local (check)	3	5	5	1	1
Fuji-102	9	9	7	5	3
IRI-353	3	5	3	5	3
K335	9	9	7	5	3
NR10157-2B-17-2	9	9	9	5	7
Palung 2	7	7	9	5	5
Rakshali	5	5	5	5	3
Rodina	9	9	7	5	5
Stejaree 45	9	9	5	3	3
Bhutan 11	9	9	5	3	3
B4190E-CW-139-29-176	7	5	9	5	3
B4448E-35R-1	7	7	9	5	3
Cheonmabyeo	9	7	7	3	3
Chhomro (check)	5	3	5	1	1
IR15579-166	7	7	9	5	3
IR23325-R-R-B-7-2-2	5	5	9	3	3
IR26036-2-2-2-3	7	7	7	5	7
MI01	7	5	5	3	3
NR10157-2B-13-1	7	7	7	5	3
NR10157-2B-13-5	5	5	1	5	5
NR10157-2B-17-1	9	5	7	5	7
NR10167-2B-7	3	5	7	5	3
NR10164-2B-14	7	3	9	5	7
NR10167-2B-16	7	7	9	5	7
NR10177-B-11	7	5	9	5	3
NR10180-B-13-3	7	5	7	5	7
NR10180-B-13-4	7	7	7	5	5
Seto Bhakunde	3	5	5	1	3

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice scale. Only Chhomro Local, Chhomro, and Seto Bhakunde gave some yield.

materials such as China 1039, Akiyudaka, and Stejaree 45 failed to set grain.

This suggests a need to evaluate more

indigenous varieties from the Himalayan belt for use in the breeding program for cold-tolerant rices. ■

Screening rice for temperature tolerance in northern Nigeria

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Most rice production in Nigeria is restricted to the wet season, with a long fallow between seasons. Irrigation schemes in the northern states provide an opportunity to overcome contingent drought and increase rice production through better land utilization.

Development of temperature-tolerant rice varieties would help reduce the long fallow in areas with 3-4 mo of cold weather (Nov-Jan/Feb) and 3-4 mo hot weather (Feb-May).

The cold season is characterized by no rainfall, high and frequent cold harmattan wind. low minimum but relatively high maximum temperature, low relative humidity, hazy and dusty atmosphere, and high evapotranspiration (Table 1).

(Harmattan is the northeasterly cold wind that blows from Europe, across the Mediterranean and Sahara desert, and down the coast of West Africa.)

Atmospheric demand for moisture (indicated by piche evaporation) is high from

Table 1. Climatological data for cold and hot months.^a Northern Nigeria, 1988.

Month	Rainfall (mm)	Temperature (°C)		Wind speed (kg/h)	Piche evaporation (ml/d)
		Maximum	Minimum		
October	0	36	23	158.40	14.5
November	0	35	20	188.22	19.5
December	0	30.4	17.3	245.47	21.9
January	0	30.9	17.6	294.92	23.9
February	0	34.3	19.7	283.20	26.6
March	0	38.8	26.0	261.55	29.7
April	5.8	40.0	28.2	243.1	21.6
May	Trace	40.3	29.3	250.2	19.8

^aCourtesy of the Meteorological Department, Sokoto Station, Nigeria.

Nov to May compared with Jul-Sep. Irrigation water, air, and soil surfaces are cold. (This also affects labor productivity.)

We screened 100 rice lines for cold tolerance in 1987-88. Lines were seeded 18 Dec 1987. Eight failed to germinate. Seedlings in the nursery exhibited stunted growth, leaf yellowing, scorched leaf tips, retarded tillering, and poor root development.

Seedlings were transplanted 18 Feb 1988 in nonreplicated 4 × 6-m microplots. Average plant height at transplanting was 6 cm. Twenty entries died after transplanting.

Irrigation was from tubewells, and was maintained at 13-15 cm depth. As general weather conditions improved toward the end of Feb, seedlings became more vigorous.

Eight entries had 100% empty glumes; incidence of sterility in the remaining 64 entries ranged from 18 to 60%. This may be attributed to high temperature and high winds at anthesis in late Mar to early Apr.

Plant height at maturity ranged from 69.4 to 95.0 cm; days to 50% flowering ranged from 105 to 142 (Table 2).

The best 18 entries were selected for further advanced yield trials 1988-89. ■

Table 2. Growth characteristics and grain yield of cultivars selected for cold tolerance.^a Nigeria, 1987-88.

Cultivar ^a	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield g/pot (2.4m ²)
RNR74229	122	83.3	1380
RTN76-2-1-1-1	127	90.4	1300
IR13538-48-2-3-2	115	79.2	1230
IR27325063-2-2	122	84.4	1180
BR161-23-59	122	75.2	1180
FAROX233-1-1-3	127	82.2	1160
C1321-2	122	72.4	1140
IR24594-272-2-2	121	95.0	1120
KUA1727	127	90.6	1120
BG367-4	105	84.4	1100
IR28210-68-4-1-3	109	80.2	1100
IR28118-138-2-3	142	90.4	1100
ITA302	122	83.4	1080
ITA121	111	69.4	1060
C1158-7	138	77.4	1040
16439	116	74.4	1040
BG276-5	105	80.0	1000
ET6279	122	80.2	1000

^aCold tolerance score for these entries is 5 by the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Phosphorus activity in genotypes with low phosphorus tolerance

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Seven P-tolerant varieties (IR28, IR29, IR30, Khonorullo, Mirikrak, Pawnbuh, and Ngoba) and their 21 cross combinations made in a diallel fashion without reciprocals were sown in upland lateritic soil deficient in P (5 ppm available P, pH 5.0). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Spacing was 20 cm between plants and between rows.

Plant tissue analysis was done 60 d after seeding (leaf) and at harvest (root, leaf, stem, panicle without grain, and sound grain). Genotypic and phenotypic

correlation coefficients were estimated, and path analysis done.

P content in leaf at 60 d showed a significant negative correlation ($r_g = -0.413$) with sound grain P (see table); other correlations were not significant. Root P had a significant, positive association with P content in stem ($r_p = 0.603$, $r_g = 0.722$), leaf ($r_p = 0.419$, $r_g = 0.507$), and sound grain ($r_p = 0.525$, $r_g = 0.588$) at both the phenotypic and genotypic levels. A significant, positive association was found between P content in stem and leaf at harvest; that between grain yield and plant was significant and negative at phenotypic and genotypic levels.

The effect of P activity through different pathways and its role in yield was determined using genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients. The genotypic correlation had a higher magnitude. The highest direct positive contribution was made by P in the root

Phenotypic and genotypic correlation^a coefficients of P content in leaf at 60 d growth, different organs at harvest, and grain yield per plant and direct contributions to yield.

	Correlation coefficients of P content ^b						Direct effect
	At 60 d growth			At harvest			
	Leaf	Root	Stem	Leaf	Panicle without grain	Grain	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	
(1)							0.230 0.280
(2) r_p	-0.093						0.211
r_g	-0.112						0.337
(3) r_p	0.044	0.603**					0.051
r_g	0.070	0.722**					0.080
(4) r_p	0.184	0.419*	0.634**				-0.514
r_g	0.185	0.507**	0.726**				-0.669
(5) r_p	-0.292	0.057	0.062	0.260			0.028
r_g	-0.347	0.075	0.065	0.288			0.038
(6) r_p	-0.353	0.525**	0.332	0.292	0.237		-0.080
r_g	-0.413*	0.588**	0.359	0.303	0.241		-0.135
(7) r_p^c	0.154	-0.039	-0.166	-0.382*	-0.232	-0.190	-
r_g^c	0.167	-0.052	-0.189	-0.418*	-0.255	-0.217	-

^a r_p , r_g phenotypic and genotypic correlation coefficients. ^bSignificant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ^cFor grain yield/plant.